

TAXONOMY OF BRAIN TUMOR CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUES: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW**Virupakshappa* & Dr. Basavraj Amarapur****

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Abstract:

The use of digital image processing has become very demanding in various areas including medical applications. There are many applications where image processing is used to understand, analyze, interpret and make decisions. The main purpose of image processing is to improve the quality of the images for human/ machine perception. The image processing techniques consist of image pre-processing, enhancement, segmentation, feature extraction and classification implemented for the detection and classification of tumor from MRI images. In this paper we analyzed already proposed brain tumor detection and classification techniques. Brain image classification is very important because it provides anatomical structure information, necessary for planning of the treatment and patient follow-up. Thus various methods are surveyed in order to get better classification accuracy in terms of specificity, sensitivity and accuracy. This survey tries to classify brain MRI images into normal, benign and malignant tumor. Classification of tumor is done with various techniques like Artificial Neural Networks, K- Nearest Neighbor, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Sequential Minimal Optimization (SMO) etc.

Key Words: Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Magnetic Resonance Image (MRI), Sequential Minimal Optimization (SMO), K- Nearest Neighbor (KNN) & Support Vector Machine (SVM)

1. Introduction:

Normally brain tumor starts by unpredictable development in the brain and usually does not spread into another parts in the body [1]. These brain tumors [2] are delegated expressed by the tissue of phylogenic origin. The ICBM issue Probabilities Atlases are used to get the earlier probabilities of various brain tissues [3]. A multi objective genetic algorithm based system has been proposed for playing out the elements of gene selection and fuzzy clustering at the same time [4]. They ascertain the arrangement of support vector machine classifiers the capacity of brain tumor classification. They goal to furnishing the human expert with effortlessly interpretable probabilistic measurements to aid the time, volume and accuracy demanding diagnostic process [5]. The Magnetic Resource Spectroscopy (MRS) strategy gives more noteworthy data than MRI techniques alone, concerning the observation, identification and measurement of biologically imperative mixes in delicate tissue [6]. They have extended the above ways to deal with incorporate nonlinear metabolite cooperation of particular cases [7]. Support Vector Machines (SVMs) are nonlinear pattern analysis models stemming from statistical learning theory whose execution and generalization capacity has been confirmed in different application spaces [8]. A diagnosis framework proficiently looks the huge limit features by genetic algorithm and sustain them to the adaptive neuro-fuzzy based classifier [9]. A computer aided diagnosis (CAD) is quickly developing in the event of cancer identification utilizing multimodality imaging [10]. Built up a segmentation strategy that utilizations likelihood to decide divided contours [11]. Recommended statistical structure analysis for MRI brain tumor segmentation. [13] Continuation of their prior work in view of theory of shape identified with gradation of benignancy of tumor in tissue region [12][14]. They presented an effective recognition of brain tumor from cerebral MRI images. The technique comprises of three stages: enhancement, segmentation and classification. [15].

Figure 1: MRI image of Brain

Numerous research works focuses are centered around the issue on account of the way that cerebral cancer is spreading among the world population. [16] Due to its antagonistic effects on influenced individuals, the cancer infections constitute a high weight on national economy and a wellspring of torment for the family and also the general public. Numerous medical imagery diagnosis frameworks [17] need to confront the issue of cells and their nuclei detachment from whatever is left of the picture content. Exhibited a programmed segmentation of malignant tumor in magnetic resonance images (MRI's) of brain utilizing optimal texture features [18]. Computer based methods of texture analysis were originally produced for use in satellite applications, geological surveys, remote sensing and other related applications [19]. MR Image texture analysis is turned out to be valuable in the identification of Alzheimer's illnesses [20].

2. Classification of Brain Tumor:

Brain tumors are generally classified into two categories: primary (Benign) and secondary (Malignant).

Primary Brain Tumors Tumors that start inside brain tissue are usually known as primary brain tumors. These tumors are characterized by the kind of tissue in which they emerge. The most well-known brain tumors are gliomas, which start in the glial (strong) tissue. There are a few sorts of gliomas, including the accompanying:

Astrocytomas emerge from little, star-molded cells called astrocytes. They may develop anyplace in the brain or spinal line. In grown-ups, astrocytomas frequently emerge in the cerebrum. In youngsters, they happen in the brain stem, the cerebrum, and the cerebellum. A review III astrocytoma is infrequently called anaplastic astrocytoma. A review IV astrocytoma is normally called glioblastoma multiforme.

Oligodendrogliomas emerge in the phones that create myelin, the greasy covering that ensures nerves. These tumors typically emerge in the cerebrum. They develop gradually and as a rule don't spread into encompassing cerebrum tissue.

Ependymomas normally create in the covering of the ventricles. They may likewise happen in the spinal cord. Despite the fact that these tumors can create at any age, they are most basic in youth and adolescence.

There are some other types of brain tumors which do not begin in glial tissue. Most common are listed below:

Meningiomas develop from the meninges. They are typically kind-hearted. Since these tumors become gradually, the mind might have the capacity to change in accordance with their nearness; meningiomas may become very expansive before they cause side effects. They happen regularly in ladies in the vicinity of 30 and 50 years old.

Schwannomas are benevolent tumors that emerge from Schwann cells, which deliver the myelin that ensures fringe nerves. Acoustic neuromas are a kind of schwannoma. They happen principally in grown-ups. These tumors influence ladies twice as regularly as men.

Craniopharyngiomas create in the area of the pituitary organ close to the hypothalamus. They are typically benevolent; however, they are in some cases considered threatening on the grounds that they can press on or harm the hypothalamus and influence essential capacities. These tumors happen frequently in kids and youths.

Germ cell tumors emerge from primitive (creating) sex cells, or germ cells. The most incessant kind of germ cell tumor in the mind is a germinoma.

Pineal region tumors happen in or around the pineal organ, a minor organ close to the focal point of the brain. The tumor can be moderate developing (pineocytoma) or quickly developing (pineoblastoma). The pineal district is extremely hard to reach, and these tumors regularly can't be evacuated.

Secondary Brain Tumors Secondary Brain tumors will be caused from cancer that starts in another part of the body. These tumors are not the same as primary brain tumors. The spread of cancer inside the body is called metastasis. Cancer that spreads to the brain is a similar sickness and has an indistinguishable name from the primary cancer. For instance, if lung cancer spreads to the brain, the illness is called metastatic lung cancer on the grounds that the cells in the secondary tumor take after irregular lung cells, not anomalous brain cells. Treatment for secondary brain tumors relies upon where the cancer began and the degree of the spread and different variables, including the patient's age general health, and reaction to past treatment.

3. Types of Imaging Techniques Used for Tumor Detection:

The improvement of radiological imaging techniques for the assessment of brain tumors has advanced altogether as of late. In any case, two modalities that assume a critical part in the assessment of brain tumors in preoperative time to confine are computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Different techniques utilized for Brain tumor recognition is portrayed underneath:

Conventional Non-Invasive X-Ray Methods: Previously, conventional non-invasive x-beam examination (radiography of the head) was the essential diagnostic strategy in neuroradiology. The benchmark projections are posteroanterior (PA) and sidelong x-beam projections of the skull. A PA projection is focused by orbitomeatal lines and gives anatomical data about the skull and frontal structures. A sidelong projection demonstrates the setup of the skull and the skull base.

Conventional Invasive X-Ray Methods: Pneumoencephalography is an imaging strategy in which the lumbar or suboccipital approach is utilized to ingrain air into the cerebral ventricles and the subarachnoid spaces in the wake of expelling roughly 10–30 mL of cerebrospinal fluid. Ventriculography is an imaging technique in which, through a trepanation opening, air is brought into every sidelong brain ventricle after the gathering of cerebrospinal fluid. These imaging x-beam methods are as of now not utilized as a part of clinical practice.

Ultrasound: Ultrasound is a broadly accessible, non-invasive diagnostic strategy without negative natural effects. Essentially, it is connected, in the essential examination of the brain in prenatal and postnatal conclusions, and in the examination of cerebral arteries. As of now, ultrasonography, utilized as a part of arranging operational technique and decision of neurosurgery access, has been supplanted by new, and more exact, neuro navigation frameworks utilizing MRI information. Ultrasound with a high-recurrence transducer can be utilized to screen changes amid brain tumor operations progressively.

Computed Tomography – CT: The fundamental CT examination of brain tumors includes standard non-contrast upgraded and contrast improved imaging. Contrasted with MR, CT is prevalent in the identification of calcification and bone abnormalities, and it is additionally less time expending. In CT diagnosis, contingent upon the sort of examination, iodinated contrast agents are regulated, in various quantities and by various modes. Iodinated contrast agents are partitioned into ionic, high-osmolar contrast agents and non-ionic, low-osmolar or iso-osmolar contrast agents. Intravenous organization of contrast agents may bring about different negative unfavorably susceptible responses, which are partitioned into right on time (inside 20 min) and late effects. By

and by, non-ionic contrast media are generally favored as, because of their low osmolarity, they result in altogether less negative effects.

Conventional MRI Techniques: Conventional MRI techniques give data about the anatomical states of brain tissue, the tumor itself, and its association with its environment. In contrast to CT, conventional MRI techniques are altogether more delicate, yet as they are nonspecific, they regularly give constrained data about tumor physiology. The conventional MRI protocol in the diagnosis of brain tumors incorporates standard T1-weighted imaging (spin echo [SE], turbo spin echo [TSE], gradient echo, three-dimensional [3D] sequences, and dynamic reviews), T2-weighted imaging (SE, quick spin echo [FSE] or TSE, and 3D sequences), "dark fluid" T2-weighted imaging (proton thickness [PD] and fluid-attenuated reversal recovery [FLAIR]), gradient echo (GRE T2, T2 * GRE, and GRE 3D T1), reversal recovery (IR) (FLAIR, T1 IR, and brief time reversal recovery [STIR]), and fat suppression (FS) (STIR and T1 FS).

Contrast Agents: Notwithstanding non-contrast upgraded imaging, magnetic resonance examination is acknowledged with contrast agents, which enhances visualization and division of the tumor. Contrast agents utilized as a part of MRI are paramagnetic substances containing gadolinium chelates; they cause shortening of the T1 and T2 unwinding times, bringing about a more grounded T1 and a lower T2 flag, and they additionally increment the contrast between two tissues with various quantities of the contrast specialist. Increment of T1 flag is more critical, contrasted and the level of shortcoming of the T2 flag; hence T1-weighted sequences are utilized after contrast organization.

Advanced MRI Techniques: Early and precise diagnosis is the main precondition of the fruitful treatment of brain tumors. The fundamental technique for deciding species diagnosis and reviewing is the histopathological examination. Biopsy is an invasive strategy with the danger of conceivable confusions. At the time of the improvement and viable utilization of present day, progressed diagnostic techniques, the part of radio diagnostic imaging modalities was not restricted to the evaluation of obsessive anatomical conditions. Progressed magnetic resonance techniques in neuroradiology assess changes at the microvascular, haemodynamic, and cell levels of brain tumors, and notwithstanding basic changes, assess changes at the metabolic and biochemical levels. Fuse of new diagnostic techniques, for example, diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI), diffusion tensor imaging (DTI), tractography, perfusion-weighted imaging (PWI), magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS), and practical MRI (fMRI), into the diagnostic protocol permits us to acquire point by point data about tumor lesions. This exhibits the best probability of precise evaluating of brain tumors in the preoperative time, permitting us to choose the most suitable remedial administration for the patients

4. Comparison of Classification Technologies:

In this Paper [21] a novel technique to distribute a MR brain image as gentle or malignant is presented. They separate the components from given MR brain tumor image, they initially utilized wavelet change which is then trailed by Laplacian Eigen maps (LE) so as to curtail the dimensions of extracted features. After classification the next stride remains image segmentation. They proposed algorithm with Gaussian Radial Basis (GRB) kernel owing to the evidence that it achieves higher efficiency. They have proposed Kernel-SVM based MR tumor image segmentation. MR brain tumor classification and segmentation have been performed on various T2-weighted MR brain images which include both malignant as well as benign tumors. They have performed our analysis on datasets available at OASIS dataset, ADNI dataset. Their algorithm has achieved better results when compared with existing MR tumor segmentation paths such as Fuzzy C-means Clustering, Clustering K-nearest neighbors, Edge-based contour approach and Otsu's technique and the quantitative validation of claim has been demonstrated

A technique for substance based image recovery of glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) and non-GBM tumors. Information decrease methods, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), were connected on the preparation sets. The Support Vector Machine and Radial Basis Function Neural Network classifiers were applied to classify the tumor. The SVM achieved a highest accuracy for classification [22]. This algorithm is intended to be a part of a CBIR scheme that can evaluate a new MR imaging study of the brain for abnormality. In the current implementation, a user has to delineate a region of interest. However, they are also implementing a entirely automated system where a new imaging study will be roughly clustered into four classes and each class will be first evaluated as normal/abnormal before proceeding to the second stage of classification as Grade 3 or Grade 4 tumor.

In this paper, they proposed a hybrid intelligent machine learning strategy for automatic grouping of cerebrum attractive reverberation pictures. They additionally proposed a Feed Forward Back-Propagation Neural Network to group contributions to ordinary or irregular. It accomplishes high characterization rate and beats as of late presented techniques while it needs a minimum number of components for order [23]. Their comes about demonstrated that Feed Forward back engendering neural network classifier utilizing Haralick and wavelet highlights give higher precision as looked at k - NN and SVM. FFNN base classifier additionally gives great specificity and affectability when contrasted with k - NN and SVM.

A three different elements of the EU FET HELICoID project were introduced in this paper. The HELICoID setup consists of two hyperspectral cameras, a scanning unit, and an illumination system. An in-vivo human brain hyperspectral image data base, has been employed as input to different supervised classification algorithms (SVM, RF, and NN) and to a spatial-spectral filtering stage (SVM-KNN). The SVM-KNN classification algorithm on the MPPA EMB01 platform is demonstrated [24]. The demonstrator showed the possibility to provided neurosurgeons with a tool to make precise real-time decisions during brain tumor resection. This tool will contribute to improved surgery results and, as a consequence, the quality of life of patients after surgery. Classification maps from the different machine learning algorithms evaluated, as well as implementation results on a many core platform, when in-vivo human brain hyperspectral images are employed as inputs, are shown as evidences of the tool potential.

They proposed a random forest (RF) based literature transmission to SVM classifier method for segmenting tumor lesions while occupying their complex characteristics. Most importantly, it is simple and fast and it also significantly outperformed the mere use of SVM or RF for tumor classification [25]. The Brain Tumor Image Segmentation Challenge (BRATS) dataset contains about 300 cases of both low-grade and high-grade gliomas. For their experiments, they selected 20 random patients with high-grade gliomas from the Brain Tumor Image Segmentation Challenge (BRATS) dataset. Using this dataset allows to compare our approach to state-of-the-art of tumor segmentation. Only FLAIR MR Images are used for testing and training the proposed framework.

An emerging technology for medical diagnosis. Preliminary results of applying two different supervised classification algorithms (Support Vector Machines and Artificial Neural Networks) to the hyperspectral database show that an automatic discrimination between healthy and tumour brain tissues from in-vitro samples is possible using exclusively their spectral information [26].

Figure 2; Process of Artificial Neural Network

An emerging technology for medical diagnosis. Preparatory consequences of applying two diverse supervised classification algorithms (Support Vector Machines and Artificial Neural Networks) to the hyperspectral database demonstrate that a programmed segregation amongst sound and tumor brain tissues from in-vitro tests is conceivable utilizing solely their phantom data [26]. This paper shows a classification conspire for separating adult brain tumors utilizing conventional MRI and rCBV maps computed from perfusion MRI. The aftereffects of multiclass classification (Table 3) represent that the most noteworthy classification precision is accomplished for metastasis (91.7%) and second rate glioma (90.9%), though the classification exactness for GBM is diminished (29.4% are classified as review III and 29.4% as metastasis). The most reduced classification rate in the multiclass issue is for the review III glioma, where the biggest bit (44.4%) is classified as review II and the littler bits as GBM (11.1%) or metastasis (11.1%).

A nonlinear classification, a portion work (Polynomial, Gaussian Radial Basis Function, and Multi-Layer Perceptron) to change the component space to a higher measurement space where a straight detachment is conceivable is proposed in this paper [27]. SVMs give another way to deal with the issue of example acknowledgment with clear associations with the basic factual learning hypothesis. They contrast drastically from equivalent methodologies, for example, neural systems: SVM preparing dependably finds a worldwide least, and their basic geometric elucidation gives fruitful ground to further examination. A SVM is to a great extent described by the selection of its piece, and SVMs in this way interface the issues they are intended for with a substantial collection of existing work on part based techniques. I trust that this instructional exercise will urge some to investigate SVMs for themselves.

SVM is a supervised learning technique, and which demonstrated remarkable performances especially for data analysis and pattern recognition is proposed in [28]. They extend their result to non-separable training data. Their experiments for constructing support-vector networks make use of two different databases for bit-mapped digit recognition, a small and a large database. In all their experiments ten separators, one for each class, are constructed. Each hyper surface makes use of the same dot product and pre-processing of the data Classification of an obscure example is done by the most extreme yield of these ten classifiers.

The classification and identification scores of brain tumor by using k-NN algorithm which is based on training of k. The Algorithm has been tested on 48 images. it achieves better accuracy [29]. KNN is a supervised algorithm which learns more if trained more. 20 samples are taken for each cases. Each case has some training data. The Algorithm has been tried on 48 pictures. The ID score for all pictures are around 95%. Their outcome demonstrated that the order and distinguishing proof scores of the cerebrum tumor pictures. Additionally, it demonstrates that separation estimations for each class. The calculation has been prepared for Manhattan separate metric.

Another component which utilizes a saliency recognition calculation is proposed in this paper. An edge-aware filtering is utilized to adjust edges of the first picture to the saliency outline improves the limits of the tumor. At that point, for characterization of tumors in brain images, an arrangement of powerful surface components is extricated from super-voxels [30]. To assess the execution of their calculation they contrast it and the characterization of Scheme of employments spatial choice backwoods arrangement for its division. Dice score is a similarity index that is measuring an overlap ratio between an algorithm's result and that of the ground truth

$$DiceScore = \frac{2TP}{(TP + FP) + (TP + FN)}$$

They compared their algorithm with one of the related works. Their results show better average Dice score for low grade tumors and comparable results for high grade tumors.

The diverse approach of data mining that can be utilized for determination and visualization of brain tumor is discussed in this paper. The imperative part in medical treatment for the brain tumor is to distinguish the area of the tumor. So that the image mining methods is the straight forward method to recognize the region of the tumor based on the MRI images [31].

A machine learning based approach for performance investigation for the review of malignant tumor types utilizing a differing feature set based on Gabor and Wavelet transformation. A few State-Of-Art classifiers are utilized for examination of the execution for the order of malignant brain tumors in Magnetic Resonance (MR) Images [32]. In this existing work they employed three state-of-art standard linear and nonlinear classifiers named K-closest Neighbor (KNN), multi-level Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Back Propagation Neural Network (BPNN). Exhibitions of the considerable number of classifiers are inspected utilizing the chosen important features utilizing different algorithms. The exhibitions of the considerable number of classifiers of each kind of brain neoplasm variation from the norm are denoted by the confusion matrix. The hybrid approach gives better classification precision in each condition compared to standalone feature extraction system. Additionally, the hybrid feature set with previous feature selection algorithm (CVM) gives most noteworthy precision with each classifier for high review malignant tumor characterization however the best outcome is accomplished in the combination of {Gabor-Wavelet + CVM + BPNN} where the accuracy rate is 97%.

A brain tumor segmentation is utilized to recognize the different stages incorporates benign, malignant and the normal. For the process toward classifying voxels, a classifier called Self Organizing Map (SOM) is utilized. It reduces the classification error rate and they give the better exactness [33]. The technique for segmenting tumor is more demanding, the reason is that brain tumor MRI images uncovered the heterogeneity in terms of their appearances, visually unclear and they request the high differing qualities in the tumor area. Brain tumors can have different sizes and shapes and may appeared at various areas. In addition to that tumor heterogeneity, tumor edges are complex. So the segmentation is done through the Self Organizing map.

A Multiobjective Optimization (MOO) based clustering technique using AMOSA (Archived Multiobjective Simulated Annealing) as the hidden optimization methodology for classification of tissue tests from disease informational indexes [34]. The execution of the proposed MOO based clustering system utilizing the ideas of AMOSA is contrasted with other state-of-art clustering algorithm like MOGASVM, Expectation Maximization Clustering (EM), K-means clustering, hierarchical average linkage clustering, SiMM-TS clustering, Self-Organizing Map (SOM) clustering and consensus clustering. Consensus clustering contains three ways to deal with troupe group, which are Cluster based Similarity Partitioning Algorithm (CSPA), Meta Clustering Algorithm (MCLA) and Hyper Graph Partitioning Algorithm (HGPA). These three group outfit procedures join the clustering arrangements which are found by EM, SOM, K-means and normal linkage grouping strategies.

A standard method for brain MRI tumor recognition and tumors classification is clarified in paper [35]. They utilize adaptive pillar K means algorithm for segmentation and two-tier classification strategy for classification. It created the best execution over the conventional classification technique. The execution of the existing framework for the brain MRI classification is superior to alternate strategies. The classification exhibitions, for example, affectability, specificity and precision additionally relatively superior to the traditional technique. From these investigations the existing framework shows it is distinctly one of the best decisions for tumor classification in brain MRI.

An automatic brain tumor identification and segmentation structure that comprises of methods from skull stripping to discovery and segmentation of brain tumors is employed with fuzzy Hopfield neural network as its last tumor segmentation technique. It delivered the higher productivity and exactness [36]. The affectability and specificity of the classification result changes for various cases in both reproduced and genuine datasets. For instance, on PDC's datasets of Patient B, Patient C and Patient G got a most extreme affectability which equals, this implies all ground truth tumorous slices were named genuine positives. Among the aggregate number of ground truth tumorous slices in PDC's dataset just 4 slices are wrongly distinguished as false negative and among non-tumorous ground truth slices, slices are wrongly identified as tumorous slices (false positives). Thus, for reproduced tumor datasets add up to false positives are 48 slices while false negatives are 26 slices, excluding S08

An examination of three distinctive intensity based feature extraction strategy for the anomalous examples in brain tumors are quickly clarified in [37]. The accompanying real classifications of brain tumor images are taken into their consideration. They are Metastatic bronchogenic carcinoma, Astrocytoma, Meningioma, sarcoma. The exploratory outcomes recommended that among the intensity based feature extraction techniques GLCM (Gray Level Co-Occurrence) strategy is demonstrating preferable outcomes over alternate strategies. From the analysis the execution of J48 Algorithm is indicating close connection with the GLCM feature extraction strategy. GLCM feature extraction methods demonstrates it is nearly connecting with the main J48 algorithm as far as the precision. This Experiment is done in an alternate measurement to demonstrate the textural feature extraction component GLCM is the best performing one to till date separated from different systems. To demonstrate the nearby correlation, they implemented this strategy.

A novel feature extraction mechanism is named as Counting Label Occurrence Matrix (CLOM) is referred in [38]. CLOM depends on the counting label of the gray level force estimations of an image and used to extricate the textural features of an image for image classification. The outcome demonstrated that the existing calculation gives preferable precision over past algorithms when tried with classifiers like KNN and BPNN. Their existing algorithm is additionally tried and contrasted and three distinctive condition of-workmanship feature extraction methods like GLCM (Gray Label Co-event Matrix) and Run length Matrix. The relative trial results are appeared in Table 2 with two standard classifiers i.e. KNN and Neural Network. CLOM based features gives the most elevated grouping precision of 89.25 for Gliomas utilizing KNN classifier and 91.3 utilizing neural system classifier.

A new hybrid technique in view of the support vector machine (SVM) and fuzzy c-means for brain tumor classification is clarified in this current casing work. Fuzzy c-means (FCM) clustering is utilized for the segmentation of the picture to detect the suspicious locale in brain MRI image. Their proposed strategy gives accurate and more effective outcome for classification of brain MRI images [39]. SVM technique with fuzzy c-means is utilized for segmentation and classification of brain MRI pictures. Genuine informational index of 120 patients MRI brain pictures have been utilized to detect "tumor" and 'non-tumor' MRI image. The delicate tissues in brain MRI pictures are divided with Double Thresholding, Morphological operations and fuzzy c-means calculation for clustering and dark level run length lattice for highlight extraction. The SVM classifier is prepared utilizing 96 brain MRI pictures, after that the rest of the 24 brain MRI pictures was utilized for testing the prepared SVM. To start with SVM is prepared by utilizing 96 MRI brain picture preparing set. Once the SVM is prepared, the classification accuracy is approved utilizing the testing set. The outcome for classification gives accurate to expansive data collections.

CBMIR(Content 87/5–Based Medical Image Retrieval) framework With enhanced feature selection technique is created utilizing a hybrid approach of "branch and bound algorithm" and " Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm" utilizing the breast cancer, Brain tumor and thyroid images and characterization is performed utilizing Fuzzy based Relevance Vector Machine (FRVM) to shape gatherings of pertinent picture features. The strategy tackled dimensionality curse problem and enhance the execution of the framework [40].

A novel approach for multi-class brain tumor classification based on sparse coding and dictionary learning method. They used a particular (per-class) dictionary learning and sparse coding classification using K-SVD algorithm. Their displayed the Sparse Coding based classification outperforms other State-Of-The-Art methods [41]. They displayed the classification achievement of the proposed algorithm using sparse coding classifier better than other classification methods it can be observed that the class 1 (normal) is classified correctly with minimum because the topological feature gives accurate information of the normal and abnormal cases. The errors occurred mainly with the class 4 (carcinoma) with error 0.14 which is divided as class 2 (glioma) and class 3 (glioplastoma) due the textural similarity in T2 MRI images of these cases. Class 3 (glioplastoma) is classified as class 2 (glioma) with error 0.0565 and class 2 (glioma) is classified as class 3 (glioplastoma) with error 0.0435. Totally, 6.25 % of the four classes are classified incorrectly.

A machine-learning calculation for order of phosphorus attractive reverberation spectroscopic imaging (31P-MRSI) information of human cerebrum tumors is representation in this paper. This outcome demonstrated that machine learning could be effectively connected for arrangement of 31P-MR spectra of cerebrum tumors [42]. They demonstrated that bolster vector machine and strategic relapse can be utilized for characterizing characterization models to segregate mind tumor from ordinary tissue in view of 31P-MRSI information at 3T. The three grouping techniques were similar in execution. Calculated relapse brought about a higher affectability, specificity and precision than both SVM techniques. The principle constraint of this review was little subject populace bringing about rather low precision. Future reviews will investigate the materialness of machine learning calculations for phosphorus MR spectroscopic information grouping in a bigger dataset. Extra reviews will investigate separating glioma subgroups utilizing machine-learning calculations in view of 31P-MRSI information.

To integrate the possibility for quick manual corrections into a fully automatic segmentation method for brain tumor images. They combined decision forest classification with conditional random field regularization for interactive segmentation of 3D medical images. Their approach has been evaluated by two different users on the BraTS2012 dataset [43]. An interactive method for semi-automatic segmentation of brain tumor images. An initial fully automatic segmentation, together with a confidence map, is showed to the user who can make corrections where necessary. These corrections are integrated into the segmentation in a second stage using a fast conditional random field segmentation approach.

A PC based technique for characterizing tumor district in the MRI brain pictures are examined in this paper. The calculation consolidates ventures for pre-processing, feature extraction and classification using neural network techniques. The extraction of surface features in the identified tumor has been accomplished by using Gabor channel. These features are utilized to prepare and group the brain tumor utilizing Artificial Neural Network classifier [44].

The CAD framework that depends on histogram adjustment and morphological picture processing techniques. In classification arrange which is the last phase of the PC helped identification frameworks, 6 classification calculations are tried in the Rapid Miner program, and these calculations are contrasted with each other with show CAD framework precision [45]. In the pre-processing stage histogram evening out method is utilized to make express the mass that can be tumor. Along these lines, the discovery of ROI is less demanding in division arrange. Returns for money invested features are extricated and then these ROIs are ordered in two general classes that are tumor cells and ordinary cells in the classification organize. The classification calculations that are K closest neighbor and Particle Swarm Optimization support vector machines (SVM) furnish a 100% accomplishment with the created framework. Later on study, parallel programming will be utilized to distinguish the extraction of ROIs features quicker. In this manner, not just high rate of accomplishment will be given, additionally the recognition procedure

will take shorter time.

This paper developed the Neural Network strategies for the classification of the magnetic resonance human brain images. Their proposed Neural Network strategy comprises of three phases, pre-processing, dimensionality reduction, and classification. In classification organize the Back-Propagation Neural Network has been utilized as a classifier to characterize subjects as ordinary or anomalous MRI brain images [46]. Test result demonstrates that the strategy is workable with exactness of 96.33%. This system is quick in execution, proficient in classification and simple in usage. As a general this framework was fruitful as it met the goals of the venture and effectively created, run and upgraded the execution of the classification procedure.

To estimate efficacy, tumor segmentation execution utilizing proposed multi-fractal feature is contrasted and that utilizing Gabor like multi-scale text on feature. The novel patient-independent tumor segmentation plan is proposed by expanding the outstanding AdaBoost algorithm. This algorithm is utilized to classify the MR images [47].

In this work another joint classification and reconstruction system to capture the hidden practical and basic data and exploit it to upgrade the signal-to noise ratio (SNR) in these features during discharge tomography (ET) reconstruction. They additionally built up another anatomy-guided ET reconstruction algorithm that all the more unmistakably separates features in the discharge reconstruction image that don't have a coordinating limit in the anatomical image [48]. The proposed technique yielded less sharp and noisy edges than asymmetrical borders when both were begun from a quick MLEM reconstruction and iterated similarly long. This shows slower merging of the high frequencies. After a quick MLEM reconstruction, the determination is not completely recouped yet. Subsequently, the edge areas are considered as outliers and the earlier urges neighboring outliers to be comparative, thus backing off the union. Utilizing the first MR division data to separate between outliers from various tissues may be an answer for this issue.

In this system a Computer Aided Diagnosis for early prediction of Brain Cancer Class utilizing texture features and neuro classification logic and back propagation artificial neural network. Their work included extraction of texture features from the given brain MRI test utilizing discrete wavelet change and morphological operation took after by neuro-classification [49]. A mechanized framework for finding brain tumour in the MRI image utilizing the straightforward image handling procedures. It is observed that the framework result in better identification of area of tumour. The extensive accuracy level is found and it extracts the vital features which are utilized to perceive the class of the tumour. Execution and accuracy of the composed framework is observed to be great. Subsequently it can track the Brain Cancer progressively and give exactness location of the class of the Brain Cancer.

An automatic classification system is proposed for tumor classification of MRI image. Their work demonstrated the impact of neural network (NN) and K-Nearest Neighbor (K-NN) calculations on tumor classification. It accomplished a good accuracy [50]. This paper introduced an automated system for finding brain tumor in the MRI image utilizing the basic image processing procedures. It is observed that the system result in better identification of area of tumor. The significant accuracy level is found and it extracts the vital elements which are utilized to perceive the class of the tumor. Execution and accuracy of the outlined system is observed to be great. Henceforth it can track the Brain Cancer progressively and give exactness recognition of the class of the Brain Cancer.

A Supervised learning algorithm joined with a pattern recognition technique was created and cross-approved in 18F-FDG PET investigations of a structure of a brain tumour implantation [51]. In this paper Decision Support System used for early diagnosis and staging of brain tumors has been developed. That applied to PET studies in a model of a brain tumour execution. Since SVM does not return any spatial data, a joint of this methodology at another one that includes spatial pattern recognition, such as Statistical Parametric Mapping, that could represent an effective way of merging the high accuracy of SVM to regional characteristics of the diseases and increasing the potential of the systems.

An automatic segmentation algorithm in view of local and global consistency with vigorous label introduction is proposed for brain tumor segmentation in multi-parametric MR images. Validation experiment comes about on multi-parametric MR images have exhibited that enhanced tumor segmentation accuracy and contrasted with state-with-the-art methods [52]. A novel methodology has been created to distinguish tumor regions by integrating statistical classification data and hierarchy of importance of inherent image structures. The recognized tumor regions are spatially minimal and solid concerning the image content, giving sufficient and strong direction to the resulting segmentation. In conjunction with a semi-supervised learning strategy under local and global consistency structure, this framework technique can be accomplish promising tumor segmentation as showed by examinations in light of multi-parametric MR images.

In this paper they misuse the ability of Back propagation neural network (BPN) and Radial Basis Function Neural network (RBFN) to classify brain MRI images to either cancerous or noncancerous tumor naturally. They indicated outperformance of RBFN algorithm when contrasted with BPN with classification accuracy of 85.71% which works as promising apparatus for classification and requires expansion in brain tumor investigation [53]. In this work, there is a major issue is choosing the ideal features to recognize classes. More optimization seductive strategy to deal with pick the best feature subset while keeping up satisfactory classification accuracy can be produced. Algorithm expansions can incorporate spatial autocorrelation by combination at various levels for the most part lessens MSE in the event of RBFN.

To design a CAD system for helping radiologists in multiclass classification of brain tumors. In this work, another hybrid machine learning system in view of the Support Vector Machine and Genetic Algorithm for brain tumor classification. They demonstrated that the GA optimization strategy has improved the general accuracy of SVM [54]. A hybrid GA-SVM used for determined the intensity, texture features and multiclass classification of the system. The test was executed and that contains essential tumors and auxiliary tumors which vary in each angle in their appearance, area, size and shape. The performance of GA-

SVM regarding singular class and general accuracy is assessed for vast dataset of 428 pictures. Besides, GA-SVM has conveyed a general accuracy of 91.7%. The review uncovers that GA-SVM gives more precise outcomes than past techniques and has been evaluated on more differentiated dataset.

In this paper presented a unique technique for 3-d brain tumour volume segmentation based totally on a parallel mobile automata structure. The evolved method turned into able to segment the brain tumour volumes quickly and appropriately using any quantity of label classification [55]. An interactive segmentation method enables customers too speedy and successfully segment the tumours in MR mind volumes. Their approach utilizes statistical seed distributions to conquer the local bias seen within the conventional cell automata framework. Also the effects display that enhanced accuracy, robustness, and competitive usability. Further, with a GPU execution, the strategy obtained consequences at interactive rates.

In this work they utilized maps of grey matter density acquired from Magnetic Resonance (MR) brain structural scans to recognize NF1 patients and sound controls with a multivariate pattern analysis system, Support Vector Machines. Up to 83% of all members were accurately grouped [56]. They proposed a multivariate analysis distinguished irregularities in brain territories not identified utilizing univariate systems. Specifically compelling are the distinctions saw in the hippocampal structures. These regions have been found to have anomalous neurophysiology in the NF1 mouse demonstrate, bringing about learning and memory issues. This information recommended that equivalent components may be available in the human disorders.

This structure attempt to utilize SVM naturally classify the brain MRI images under two classifications, either normal or abnormal brain which alludes to brain tumour. Utilizing feature vector picked up from the MRI images, SVM classifiers were utilized to classify the images [57]. The primary inspiration of this work is to utilize wavelet rough coefficient of a Brain MRI as the contribution for SVM. Through a machine learning strategy, they would like to accomplish better exactness and accuracy in interpreting a normal and abnormal brain images.

An intelligent system was intended to diagnose the brain tumor through MRI utilizing image processing clustering algorithms, such as Fuzzy C Means along with intelligent optimization tools, like Genetic Algorithm and Particle Swarm Optimization [58]. The normal classification error of GA is 0.078%. The normal accuracy GA is 89.6%. PSO gives best classification accuracy and normal error rate. The Average classification mistake of PSO is 0.059% and the accuracy is 92.8% and tumor detection is 98.87%. The normal classification blunder is diminished when the quantity of test was expanded. The outcomes gave generous proof that to brain tumor division of PSO algorithm performed well.

In this work designed the Kernel based methods likewise, Support Vector Machine for the classification of volume of MRI data. Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) is one of the new algorithms can be executed on existing equipment and sufficiently quick [59]. Their work includes of utilizing SVM to classify the information which is MRI Brain into ordinary and irregular classification. Likewise, they plan to demonstrate that this kernel strategy will get more precise outcome. Other than that, the usage of FPGA as equipment re-configurable will be watched so that this innovation will keep to maintain image processing in various medicinal applications. SVM is really couldn't work precisely for an expansive data because of the preparation many-sided quality of SVM is highly based on the size of data. In this framework portrays a computer-based strategy for characterizing tumor region in the brain utilizing MRI images. Their proposed algorithm includes stages for pre-processing, image segmentation, feature extraction and image classification utilizing neural network procedures [60].

5. Conclusion:

In this paper we have analyzed various brain tumor detection and classification techniques. The manual procedure that most radiologists adopt is very time consuming and causes eye fatigue. Hence an automated classification system is required. In our paper we have highlighted many classification algorithms such as ANN, SVM, KNN, SOM, etc. Depending on the problem different techniques can be choose. A classification algorithm alone cannot classify correctly because classification accuracy depends on how well you choose previous image processing methods you applied such as image pre-processing, image enhancement, image segmentation, and feature extraction. We have mentioned various combinations of these techniques along with their classification accuracies. Hence this paper will be beneficial for the people looking for the classification of brain tumours from MRI images. This paper on brain tumor classification system is expected to provide valuable diagnosis techniques for the Physicians.

6. References:

1. Badran, Ehab F., Esraa Galal Mahmoud, and Nadder Hamdy. "An algorithm for detecting brain tumors in MRI images." In Computer Engineering and Systems (ICCES), 2010 International Conference on, pp. 368-373. IEEE, 2010.
2. Moore, Kraig, and Lyndon Kim. "Primary brain tumors: Characteristics, practical diagnostic and treatment approaches." In Glioblastoma, pp. 43-75. Springer New York, 2010.
3. Wang, Tao, Irene Cheng, and Anup Basu. "Fully automatic brain tumor segmentation using a normalized Gaussian Bayesian classifier and 3D fluid vector flow." In Image Processing (ICIP), 2010 17th IEEE International Conference on, pp. 2553-2556. IEEE, 2010.
4. Mukhopadhyay, Anirban, Ujjwal Maulik, and Sanghamitra Bandyopadhyay. "Simultaneous informative gene selection and clustering through multiobjective optimization." In Evolutionary Computation (CEC), 2010 IEEE Congress on, pp. 1-8. IEEE, 2010.
5. Van Gestel, Tony, Johan AK Suykens, Gert Lanckriet, Annemie Lambrechts, Bart De Moor, and Joos Vandewalle. "Bayesian framework for least-squares support vector machine classifiers, Gaussian processes, and kernel Fisher discriminant analysis." *Neural computation* 14, no. 5 (2002): 1115-1147.

6. Simonetti, Arjan W., Willem J. Melssen, Marinette van der Graaf, Geert J. Postma, ArendHeerschap, and Lutgarde MC Buydens. "A chemometric approach for brain tumor classification using magnetic resonance imaging and spectroscopy." *Analytical Chemistry* 75, no. 20 (2003): 5352-5361.
7. Lukas, Lukas, Andy Devos, Johan AK Suykens, Leentje Vanhamme, Franklyn A. Howe, Carles Majós, A. Moreno-Torres et al. "Brain tumor classification based on long echo proton MRS signals." *Artificial intelligence in medicine* 31, no. 1 (2004): 73-89.
8. Andrew, Alex M. "An Introduction to Support Vector Machines and Other Kernel-Based Learning Methods by Nello Christianini and John Shawe-Taylor, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2000, xiii+ 189 pp., ISBN 0-521-78019-5 (Hbk,£ 27.50)." (2000): 687-689.
9. Das, Arpita, and Mahua Bhattacharya. "A study on prognosis of brain tumors using fuzzy logic and genetic algorithm based techniques." In *Bioinformatics, Systems Biology and Intelligent Computing, 2009. IJCBS'09. International Joint Conference on*, pp. 348-351. IEEE, 2009.
10. Das, Arpita, and Mahua Bhattacharya. "A study on prognosis of brain tumors using fuzzy logic and genetic algorithm based techniques." In *Bioinformatics, Systems Biology and Intelligent Computing, 2009. IJCBS'09. International Joint Conference on*, pp. 348-351. IEEE, 2009.
11. Li, Huai, Yue Wang, KJ Ray Liu, S-CB Lo, and Matthew T. Freedman. "Computerized radiographic mass detection. I. Lesion site selection by morphological enhancement and contextual segmentation." *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 20, no. 4 (2001): 289-301.
12. Xuan, Xiao, and Qingmin Liao. "Statistical structure analysis in MRI brain tumor segmentation." In *Image and Graphics, 2007. ICIG 2007. Fourth International Conference on*, pp. 421-426. IEEE, 2007.
13. Jang, J-SR. "ANFIS: adaptive-network-based fuzzy inference system." *IEEE transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics* 23, no. 3 (1993): 665-685.
14. Kharrat, Ahmed, NacéraBenamrane, Mohamed Ben Messaoud, and Mohamed Abid. "Detection of brain tumor in medical images." In *Signals, Circuits and Systems (SCS), 2009 3rd International Conference on*, pp. 1-6. IEEE, 2009.
15. Hrebień, Maciej, Piotr Steć, Tomasz Nieczkowski, and Andrzej Obuchowicz. "Segmentation of breast cancer fine needle biopsy cytological images." *International Journal of Applied Mathematics and Computer Science* 18, no. 2 (2008): 159-170.
16. <http://www.lapresse.tn/archives/archives270205/societe/grandes.html>
17. M. Lee and W. Street "Dynamic learning of shapes for automatic object recognition", *Proceedings of the 17th Workshop Machine Learning of Spatial Knowledge*, Stanford, CA, pp. 44-49, 2000.
18. Sasikala, M., N. Kumaravel, and L. Subhashini. "Automatic tumor segmentation using optimal texture features." (2006): 62-62.
19. Zuna I. , Schad L.R. and Bluml S. (1993): 'MR tissue characterization of intracranial tumors by means of texture analysis', *Magnetic Resonance Imaging*, I 1, pp. 889-896.
20. Nick C. Fox and Peter A. Freeborough. (1998): 'MR Image Texture analysis Applied to the diagnosis and tracking of Alzheimer's disease', *IEEE Trans. on Medical Imaging*, 17(3), pp.475-479.
21. Singh, Rahul, Prateek Agarwal, and Mahua Bhattacharya. "MR brain tumor detection employing Laplacian Eigen maps and kernel support vector machine." In *Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM), 2016 IEEE International Conference on*, pp. 827-830. IEEE, 2016.
22. Dube, Shishir, Suzie El-Saden, Timothy F. Cloughesy, and Usha Sinha. "Content based image retrieval for MR image studies of brain tumors." In *Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society, 2006. EMBS'06. 28th Annual International Conference of the IEEE*, pp. 3337-3340. IEEE, 2006.
23. Raghtate, Ganesh S., and Suresh S. Salankar. "Automatic Brain MRI Classification Using Modified Ant Colony System and Neural Network Classifier." In *Computational Intelligence and Communication Networks (CICN), 2015 International Conference on*, pp. 1241-1246. IEEE, 2015.
24. Salvador, R., H. Fabelo, R. Lazcano, S. Ortega, D. Madroñal, G. M. Callicó, E. Juárez, and C. Sanz. "Demo: HELICoiD tool demonstrator for real-time brain cancer detection." In *Design and Architectures for Signal and Image Processing (DASIP), 2016 Conference on*, pp. 237-238. IEEE, 2016.
25. Amiri, Samya, IslemRekik, and Mohamed Ali Mahjoub. "Deep random forest-based learning transfer to SVM for brain tumor segmentation." In *Advanced Technologies for Signal and Image Processing (ATSIP), 2016 2nd International Conference on*, pp. 297-302. IEEE, 2016.
26. Ortega, S., Gustavo Marrero Callicó, M. L. Plaza, R. Camacho, H. Fabelo, and Roberto Sarmiento. "Hyperspectral database of pathological in-vitro human brain samples to detect carcinogenic tissues." In *Biomedical Imaging (ISBI), 2016 IEEE 13th International Symposium on*, pp. 369-372. IEEE, 2016.
27. Burges, Christopher JC. "A tutorial on support vector machines for pattern recognition." *Data mining and knowledge discovery* 2, no. 2 (1998): 121-167.
28. Cortes, Corinna, and Vladimir Vapnik. "Support-vector networks." *Machine learning* 20, no. 3 (1995): 273-297.
29. Sudharani, K., T. C. Sarma, and K. Satya Rasad. "Intelligent Brain Tumor lesion classification and identification from MRI images using k-NN technique." In *Control, Instrumentation, Communication and Computational Technologies (ICCICCT), 2015 International Conference on*, pp. 777-780. IEEE, 2015.

30. Kadkhodaei, M., S. Samavi, N. Karimi, H. Mohaghegh, S. M. R. Soroushmehr, K. Ward, A. All, and K. Najarian. "Automatic segmentation of multimodal brain tumor images based on classification of super-voxels." In Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC), 2016 IEEE 38th Annual International Conference of the, pp. 5945-5948. IEEE, 2016.
31. Patel, Mr Dharmesh. "A Survey on Image Mining Techniques for Brain Tumor Classification." International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology 1, no. 4: 592-595.
32. Vidyarthi, Ankit, and Namita Mittal. "Performance analysis of Gabor-Wavelet based features in classification of high grade malignant brain tumors." In Systems Conference (NSC), 2015 39th National, pp. 1-6. IEEE, 2015.
33. Dharshini, R., and S. Hemanandhini. "Brain tumor segmentation based on Self Organising Map and Discrete Wavelet Transform." In Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI), 2016 International Conference on, pp. 1-9. IEEE, 2016.
34. Acharya, Sudipta, Sriparna Saha, and Yamini Thadisina. "Multi objective Simulated Annealing-Based Clustering of Tissue Samples for Cancer Diagnosis." IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics 20, no. 2 (2016): 691-698.
35. S. Murugavalli. "Brain tumour classification using two-tier classifier with adaptive segmentation technique." IET Computer Vision 10, no. 1 (2016): 9-17.
36. Megersa, Yehualashet, and Getachew Alemu. "Brain tumor detection and segmentation using hybrid intelligent algorithms." In AFRICON, 2015, pp. 1-8. IEEE, 2015.
37. Kumar, B. Sathees, and R. AnbuSelvi. "Feature extraction using image mining techniques to identify brain tumors." In Innovations in Information, Embedded and Communication Systems (ICIIECS), 2015 International Conference on, pp. 1-6. IEEE, 2015.
38. Nagpal, Jyoti, Ankit Vidyarthi, and Namita Mittal. "CLOM: Counting label occurrence matrix for feature extraction in MR images." In Signal Processing and Communication (ICSC), 2015 International Conference on, pp. 216-221. IEEE, 2015.
39. Singh, Amritpal. "Detection of brain tumor in MRI images, using combination of fuzzy c-means and SVM." In Signal Processing and Integrated Networks (SPIN), 2015 2nd International Conference on, pp. 98-102. IEEE, 2015.
40. Rajalakshmi, T., and R. I. Minu. "Improving relevance feedback for content based medical image retrieval." In Information Communication and Embedded Systems (ICICES), 2014 International Conference on, pp. 1-5. IEEE, 2014.
41. Al-Shaikhli, Saif Dawood Salman, Michael Ying Yang, and Bodo Rosenhahn. "Brain tumor classification using sparse coding and dictionary learning." In Image Processing (ICIP), 2014 IEEE International Conference on, pp. 2774-2778. IEEE, 2014.
42. Er, Fusun Citak, Gokce Hale Hatay, Emre Okeer, Muhammed Yildirim, Bahattin Hakyemez, and Esin Ozturk-Isik. "Classification of phosphorus magnetic resonance spectroscopic imaging of brain tumors using support vector machine and logistic regression at 3T." In Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC), 2014 36th Annual International Conference of the IEEE, pp. 2392-2395. IEEE, 2014.
43. Bauer, Stefan, Nicole Porz, Raphael Meier, Alessia Pica, Johannes Slotboom, Roland Wiest, and Mauricio Reyes. "Interactive segmentation of MR images from brain tumor patients." In Biomedical Imaging (ISBI), 2014 IEEE 11th International Symposium on, pp. 862-865. IEEE, 2014.
44. Zhu, Yan, and Zhu Yan. "Computerized tumor boundary detection using a Hopfield neural network." IEEE transactions on medical imaging 16, no. 1 (1997): 55-67.
45. Ulku, Eyup Emre, and Ali Yilmaz Camurcu. "Computer aided brain tumor detection with histogram equalization and morphological image processing techniques." In Electronics, Computer and Computation (ICECCO), 2013 International Conference on, pp. 48-51. IEEE, 2013.
46. Ibrahim, Walaa Hussein, Ahmed AbdelRhman Ahmed Osman, and Yusra Ibrahim Mohamed. "MRI brain image classification using neural networks." In Computing, Electrical and Electronics Engineering (ICEEEE), 2013 International Conference on, pp. 253-258. IEEE, 2013.
47. Islam, Atiq, Syed MS Reza, and Khan M. Iftakharuddin. "Multifractal texture estimation for detection and segmentation of brain tumors." IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering 60, no. 11 (2013): 3204-3215.
48. Vunckx, Kathleen, Simon R. Arridge, Alexandre Bousse, Daniil Kazantsev, Stefano Pedemonte, Sébastien Ourselin, and Brian F. Hutton. "Unifying global and local statistical measures for anatomy-guided emission tomography reconstruction." In Nuclear Science Symposium and Medical Imaging Conference (NSS/MIC), 2012 IEEE, pp. 2161-2165. IEEE, 2012.
49. Gupta, Vikas, and Kaustubh S. Sagale. "Implementation of classification system for brain cancer using back propagation network and MRI." In Engineering (NUICONE), 2012 Nirma University International Conference on, pp. 1-4. IEEE, 2012.
50. Al-Badarneh, Amer, Hassan Najadat, and Ali M. Alraziqi. "A classifier to detect tumor disease in MRI brain images." In Proceedings of the 2012 International Conference on Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining (ASONAM 2012), pp. 784-787. IEEE Computer Society, 2012.
51. Grosso, E., M. López, C. Salvatore, F. Gallivanone, G. Di Grigoli, S. Valtorta, R. Moresco et al. "A Decision Support System for the assisted diagnosis of brain tumors: A feasibility study for 18 F-FDG PET preclinical studies."

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In Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC), 2012 Annual International Conference of the IEEE, pp. 6255-6258. IEEE, 2012.

52. Li, Hongming, and Yong Fan. "Label propagation with robust initialization for brain tumor segmentation." In Biomedical Imaging (ISBI), 2012 9th IEEE International Symposium on, pp. 1715-1718. IEEE, 2012.
53. Deepa, S. N., and B. Aruna Devi. "Artificial neural networks design for classification of brain tumour." In Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI), 2012 International Conference on, pp. 1-6. IEEE, 2012.
54. Sachdeva, Jainy, Vinod Kumar, Indra Gupta, Niranjana Khandelwal, and Chirag Kamal Ahuja. "Multiclass brain tumor classification using ga-svm." In Developments in E-systems Engineering (DeSE), 2011, pp. 182-187. IEEE, 2011.
55. Kim, Edward, TianShen, and Xiaolei Huang. "A parallel cellular automata with label priors for interactive brain tumor segmentation." In Computer-Based Medical Systems (CBMS), 2010 IEEE 23rd International Symposium on, pp. 232-237. IEEE, 2010.
56. Duarte, Joao, Maria Ribeiro, Ines Violante, Gil Cunha, M. Al-Rawi, J. P. Cunha, and Miguel Castelo-Branco. "Multivariate pattern analysis of brain structure: A diagnostic tool for Neurofibromatosis type 1." In Bioengineering (ENBENG), 2011. ENBENG 2011. 1st Portuguese Meeting in, pp. 1-4. IEEE, 2011.
57. Abdullah, Noramalina, Umi Kalthum Ngah, and Shalihatin Azlin Aziz. "Image classification of brain MRI using support vector machine." In Imaging Systems and Techniques (IST), 2011 IEEE International Conference on, pp. 242-247. IEEE, 2011.
58. Gopal, N. Nandha, and M. Karnan. "Diagnose brain tumor through MRI using image processing clustering algorithms such as Fuzzy C Means along with intelligent optimization techniques." In Computational Intelligence and Computing Research (ICCIC), 2010 IEEE International Conference on, pp. 1-4. IEEE, 2010.
59. Othman, MohdFauzi Bin, Norarmalina Abdullah, and Nur Aizudin Bin Ahmad Rusli. "An overview of MRI brain classification using FPGA implementation." In Industrial Electronics & Applications (ISIEA), 2010 IEEE Symposium on, pp. 623-628. IEEE, 2010.
60. Badran, Ehab F., Esraa Galal Mahmoud, and Nadder Hamdy. "An algorithm for detecting brain tumors in MRI images." In Computer Engineering and Systems (ICES), 2010 International Conference on, pp. 368-373. IEEE, 2010.